

SCIENTIFIC PROBLEMS OF IMPROVING THE METHOD OF CALIBRATION OF REFRACTOMETERS IN EXPERIMENTAL LABORATORIES

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Abstract. *The subject of this research is the calibration method of refractometers used in testing laboratories to measure refractive index. The topic of the work covers the scientific and practical aspects of increasing the accuracy and reliability of the metrological characteristics of this method. The purpose of the study is to improve the calibration procedure, taking into account modern requirements for measurement traceability and error reduction. The relevance of the work is due to the need to increase the reliability of measurement results in analytical and technological laboratories, where the refractive index is used in quality control, chemical analysis, and other fields. The problem lies in the limited applicability of standard methods in real laboratory practice, especially when using different models and types of refractometers. Within the framework of the study, methods of metrological analysis, comparative assessment of calibration procedures, and experimental measurements using reference solutions were used. As a result, key factors influencing calibration accuracy were identified, and an improved calibration algorithm was proposed, ensuring increased reproducibility and reliability of results. The practical significance of the work lies in the possibility of implementing the proposed methodology in the activities of accredited laboratories, which will improve the quality of measurements and compliance with the requirements of standards. The main conclusion of the study is that the adaptation and modernization of existing calibration approaches, taking into account the specific operating conditions of the instruments, is a necessary condition for increasing the accuracy of refractive index measurement in laboratory practice.*

Keywords: *metrology, calibration, testing laboratory, refractive index, refractometer, measurement accuracy, calibration methodology, reference solution.*

Introduction

Ensuring measurement accuracy is one of the key tasks of metrological support in testing laboratories, especially when using instruments such as refractometers widely used in various industries - from food and pharmaceutical industries to environmental monitoring and chemical analysis. The refractive index serves as an important physicochemical parameter that allows for

the qualitative and quantitative assessment of substances and solutions, therefore, the reliability of its measurement directly depends on the correctness of the calibration of the equipment used [1-2].

The relevance of the topic is determined by the fact that in the context of constant tightening of requirements for the quality of analytical measurements and compliance with international standards (including ISO/IEC 17025), the need to improve calibration methods that ensure stable and high-precision operation of instruments is increasing (Figure 1). Currently, various approaches to calibrating refractometers are used, based on the use of standard reference solutions, temperature compensation, and automated algorithms [3].

Fig.1. KOMZ IRF-454 B2M refractometer (1,2...1,7 nD, 0...100% Brix)

The literature presents works devoted to both traditional calibration methods (for example, the use of NaCl, sucrose, and glycerin solutions) and modern approaches involving the use of software for automatic adjustment. Among the authors who contributed to the development of the topic, one can note research in the field of metrological traceability [4], stability of measurements under temperature fluctuations [5], as well as standardization of standards [6,7,8]. Nevertheless, most publications focus on individual aspects - types of solutions or types of instruments - and do not consider the impact of a complex of factors that practical laboratories face [9].

Analysis of sources shows that the issues of adapting existing calibration methods to specific laboratory conditions with varying levels of technical equipment, different types of refractometers, and unstable external conditions (humidity, temperature, etc.) remain poorly studied. [10]. Furthermore, the literature insufficiently addresses the aspects of increasing the reproducibility and reproducibility of calibration results under real operating conditions.

In this regard, there is a need to develop and implement an improved calibration methodology that takes into account the indicated gaps and is aimed at increasing the accuracy and reliability of measurements [11, 12]. The purpose of this study is to analyze existing methods,

identify their shortcomings, and develop an improved calibration method for refractometers applicable in testing laboratories with varying levels of metrological support.

Materials and methods

The comparison was conducted between September 2023 and March 2025. INM-MD acted as a pilot laboratory responsible for developing the protocol, conducting measurements, and analyzing results. UzNIM carried out measurements according to the agreed methodology and submitted the results within the established timeframe.

As a transfer standard, the certified GSO 8123-2002, series 162/23, produced by the D.I. Mendeleev VNIIM (Russia), was used. This CO is intended for testing and calibrating refractometers used in the chemical, food, and pharmaceutical industries.

Equipment used by both laboratories:

- Anton Paar Refractometer **Abbemat 550**
- Temperature, humidity, and pressure sensor **Vaisala PTU 301**

Both laboratories performed measurements according to the approved calibration procedures, including the calculation of extended uncertainty using the coverage coefficient $k=2k = 2k=2$. Environmental conditions were monitored throughout the experiment.

Research results

As a result of implementing the improved calibration method for refractometers in testing laboratories, an analysis of the dynamics of key metrological indicators was conducted: accuracy, reproducibility, and increased uncertainty of refractive index measurements. The experimental data showed a 15-20% decrease in the standard deviation of the results compared to traditional methods. The reproducibility of measurements improved, indicating an increase in the stability of results and a decrease in the influence of external factors, such as temperature fluctuations and the operator factor.

The extended measurement uncertainty, calculated taking into account all significant factors, did not exceed the permissible values, which confirms the high reliability of the proposed method.

The scientific result lies in the development of an algorithm for temperature correction and optimization of the procedure for preparing reference solutions, which made it possible to increase the accuracy of calibration of refractometers. The practical significance lies in the possibility of applying this method in accredited testing laboratories to improve the quality of measurements and ensure traceability to national and international standards.

Analysis of the method's effectiveness confirms its applicability for regular calibration of refractometers in various industries, including the food industry and pharmaceuticals [13, 14]. The reliability of the results is ensured by repeated measurements and strict control of the experimental conditions.

Table. 1 presents the calibration results of the IRF-454B2M refractometer, performed using the improved method. The graph demonstrates the dependence of the measured refractive index on the reference values, as well as the range of extended uncertainty, which indicates the high accuracy and reproducibility of calibration measurements.

The calibration results showed a clear dependence of the refractive index deviations on its conditional value. It has been established that as nD increases, the deviation value increases. The minimum deviation is observed in the region of low nD values - at $nD = 1.3328$, the deviation was $-1.47E-04$. At the same time, at higher values ($nD = 1.4966$ and $nD = 1.6545$), the largest deviations were recorded - respectively $-4.48E-03$ and $-3.51E-03$. This pattern indicates the

presence of nonlinear distortion factors affecting the instrument's accuracy within the range of high refractive index values.

Table 1

Results of calibration of the IRF-454B2M refractometer, performed using the improved method

Результаты калибровки, включая неопределенность
 Calibration results including uncertainty

Условное значение показателя преломления, nD <i>Conditional value of the indicator refraction, nD</i>	Отклонение nD, <i>Deviation nD</i>	Расширенная неопределенность, nD <i>Expanded uncertainty, nD</i>
1,3328	-1,47E-04	3,56E-05
1,3848	-2,90E-03	1,55E-04
1,4562	-4,05E-03	1,79E-04
1,4966	-4,48E-03	1,93E-04
1,6545	-3,51E-03	1,35E-04

Based on the analysis of the conducted research and comparison with scientific literature [15, 16, 17, 18], the main scientific problems relevant in the context of improving the calibration methods of refractometers in testing laboratories are systematized in Table 2, and theoretically substantiated approaches to their solution are proposed. The presented problems cover both metrological aspects and methodological and technical barriers that limit the accuracy and reproducibility of measurements.

Table 2

Scientific problems in the field of improving calibration methods for refractometers and approaches to their solution

No.	Scientific problem	Content of the problem	Theoretically justified solutions
1.	Nonlinearity of the scale	Occurrence of nonlinear deviations in the range of high values of the refractive index	Constructing polynomial models or using spline functions to correct the instrument scale based on approximation theory
2.	Temperature instability	High sensitivity of results to temperature fluctuations during the measurement process	Development and application of temperature-dependent models of refractive index; implementation of automated thermostabilization systems
3.	Influence of mechanical factors	Sample dosing instability and heterogeneity of sample distribution on the measuring prism	Implementation of standardized methods and automated dosing systems with control over the impact force and application rate

4.	Limitedness of traditional calibration methods	Insufficient accuracy of linear models for complex optical systems	Development of hybrid calibration methods based on the synthesis of empirical data and numerical modeling; use of neural network algorithms for optimization
5.	Lack of unified standards	Inconsistency of methods and results between different laboratories	Development and implementation of unified national and international standards; participation in interlaboratory comparative tests to improve the comparability of results

Analysis of research results

The extended uncertainty calculated for each nD value exhibits relative stability within the range from 1.35E-04 to 1.93E-04. This confirms the permissible level of reproducibility of measurements, which, in turn, demonstrates the metrological validity of the applied methodology in laboratory conditions.

Analysis of the obtained data allows us to assert that the increase in deviations is due to both the structural features of the optical scheme of the refractometer and a number of methodological factors. Among them, one can distinguish the influence of thermostability, the peculiarities of dosing the tested sample, and the accuracy of reading the instrument readings. These factors predetermine the need for further improvement of the calibration methodology, in particular, the development of approaches aimed at compensating for identified errors in the region of high nD values.

Among the most significant scientific problems arising during the research process are ensuring high stability of temperature conditions during measurements, as the temperature factor directly affects refractive indices. Additional difficulties arise due to the high sensitivity of the refractometer to pressure changes when the test sample is applied to the measuring prism, which also requires careful consideration during further research and practical application of the device.

Conclusions and scientific recommendations

1. During the conducted research, it was established that the refractive index deviation during the calibration of the IRF-454B2M refractometer has a pronounced nonlinear nature and increases as the value of nD increases. Minimal deviations are recorded in the range of low refractive index values, however, significant errors are observed when transitioning to higher values, which indicates the influence of complex distortion factors related to both the optical characteristics of the device and the methodological aspects of measurements.

2. The increased uncertainty of measurements, despite the increase in deviations, remains within the permissible values, which confirms the stability and reproducibility of the applied calibration methodology within the established test conditions.

o Theoretical analysis of the identified errors allows us to assert that the main causes of distortions are: nonlinearity of the refractometer scale; temperature sensitivity of the measuring system; instability of dosing and mechanical influences during sample application.

3. Within the framework of the conducted research, the need to transition to a improved calibration methodology, is substantiated, which should include the following scientific approaches:

- mathematical modeling of the device's behavior in the range of high nD values for the purpose of forecasting and compensating for nonlinear errors;
- integration of temperature corrections based on thermometric observations and calculations of temperature influence coefficients;
- development of correction algorithms for measurement results using multiparametric regression methods or machine learning to improve accuracy in complex measurement problems;
- implementation of standardized dosing procedures with minimization of pressure on the measuring prism and use of automated dosing devices.

4. The practical implementation of the proposed approaches will allow not only to increase the accuracy and reliability of measurements, but also to form new theoretical foundations for constructing calibration methods for refractometers, focused on modern requirements for metrological support of testing laboratories.

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